

Aggregation Properties of Anions of Fluorescein and Halofluorescein Dyes*

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A systematic spectral study of the aggregation characteristics of halofluorescein dyes has been carried out with a view to understanding the mechanism of dye aggregation. The absorption spectra of fluorescein and some of its halogen derivatives have been obtained as a function of concentration. Their monomer spectra have been compared and the effect of substitution of polarizable halogen atoms has been analysed. In concentrated solutions the dyes dimerize. The dimerization constants (K) of these dyes are reported. The values of K in three solvents, namely, water, ethanol and glycerol have been studied and attempts have been made to correlate these values. The thermodynamic parameters are calculated and they are observed to reveal some interesting problems involved in the process of dimerization.

It is well known that aqueous solutions of many dyes show remarkable changes in their absorption spectra as the concentration of the dye in the solution is gradually increased¹⁻³. These changes are attributed to the aggregation of dyes in solution^{3,4,5}. The first stage of aggregation is, however, assumed to be the formation of dimers only⁶. In a dimer molecule, the component molecules are held together by forces whose nature is still not very well understood. A number of mechanisms have been suggested by Rabinowitch and Epstein¹, Sheppard *et al.*⁷, Förster⁸ and many others⁹⁻¹¹. Since the process does not stop at the dimer stage, the phenomenon has been associated with the additive forces of the van der Waal's type. But a correlation between the extent of aggregation and oscillator strength of the molecule is not always observed.

A systematic study of the aggregation characteristics of dyes from spectrophotometric data has become a useful field of research because of its possible application in understanding such phenomena as energy transfer in biological systems¹² and photographic materials, hypochromism and conformation of polypeptides¹³, metachromasia¹⁴ and staining properties of dyes for biological specimens¹⁵ etc. It has also been used for studying active sites on adsorbates like montmorillonite¹⁶ and conversely to study the mode of adsorption of dye on crystals of known lattice structure such as AgCl, mica etc.¹⁷ Furthermore, spectral changes produced on aggregation have been utilised to predict the relative geometry of the component molecules in the aggregate by the application of the exciton theory as developed for weakly coupled systems and van der Waal's aggregates.^{18,19}

To further the efforts in the understanding of the nature of forces responsible for aggregation, we report here the aggregation properties of halogen substituted fluorescein dyes under identical experimental conditions. The effect of substitution of more polarizable

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and larger Br and I atoms on aggregation and optical properties of fluorescein may throw some light on the contribution of dispersion forces and steric factors on dye aggregation. The studies have been made at pH 12 at which these dyes exist as doubly charged anions.

EXPERIMENTAL

The commercial samples of fluorescein (FI), di-chlorofluorescein (FCl_2), di-iodofluorescein (FI_2), eosin (FIBr_4), erythrosin (FI_4), phloxin (FCl_4Br_4) and rose bengal (FCl_4I_4) were carefully purified by passing an alkaline solution through alumina column followed by precipitation with HCl. The process of dissolution in alkali and precipitation with HCl was repeated a number of times until the molar extinction value was found constant. The absorption spectra were recorded with a Beckmann DU spectrophotometer.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A series of spectra for each dye were recorded as the concentration was gradually increased. With increasing dye concentration, deformation of the monomer spectrum

Fig. 1. Normalized absorption spectra of rose bengal in water at pH 12

was observed for each dye solution although the concentration at which the deformation appeared varied in the order :

Fig. 1 shows the normalized absorption spectra of rose bengal. Due to high extinction values of the dyes, the absorption spectra of concentrated solutions were taken by sandwiching a drop of the dye solution between two glass plates which fit the Beckman cell holder. The technique for the calculation of the mole fraction of monomer (x) at any given concentration from the absorption spectra of the dye solutions has been discussed in a previous communication²⁰.

The values of the dimerization constant K were calculated at 28° by the method described earlier²⁰ in three different solvents namely, water, ethanol and glycerol. The data are recorded in table 1. This table also shows the monomer peak positions λ_{max} and the molar extinction values (ϵ_{max}) of all the dyes in aqueous solutions at pH 12.

TABLE 1

Monomer peak positions λ_{max} and intensities ϵ_{max} for fluorescein and halofluorescein dyes in aqueous solution. The last three columns give the values of the dimerization constants K of these dyes in the three different solvents at 28° and pH 12
(D = dielectric constant)

Dye	λ_{max} (nm)	$\epsilon_{max} \times 10^{-4}$ (litre/mole/cm)	K at 28°		
			Water $D = 78.54$	Glycerol $D = 39.22$	Ethanol $D = 23.55$
F1	491	8.26	5	3.9	3.6
F1Cl ₂	503	9.20	60		
F1I ₂	510	9.50	83	67	59
F1Br ₄	518	9.90	110	91	77
F1I ₄	526	10.25	140		
F1Cl ₄ Br ₄	534	10.35	190		
F1Cl ₄ I ₄	541	10.50	250	182	167

Sheppard and Geddes⁷, in their early studies on all classes of water soluble dyes, observed that the substitution of halogens in fluorescein ion such as in eosin and erythrosin, improved the conformity of their solutions to Beer's law. This was explained by suggesting that the substituted halogen atoms, being coplanar with the ring, inhibit optical coupling by their large atomic sizes. The two planar dye ions are thereby sterically hindered in their approach to within 4 Å, and aggregation is thus prevented. The present detailed study of spectral properties of this series of dyes leads to an opposite result. From Table 1 we find that the equilibrium constant for dimer formation increases with increasing halo-substitution and also by substitution of heavier halogens. The question may naturally be asked : which property of the molecules changes thereby promoting aggregation ?

A General Discussion of the Absorption Spectra : In Fig. 2 are recorded the complete absorption spectra of fluorescein and halofluoresceins. One striking feature which is thus

brought out is that the longest wave intense band is gradually shifted towards longer wavelength with concomittant increase in intensity in the order :

Fig. 2. Absorption spectra of fluorescein and halo fluorescein dyes in dilute solution at pH 12.

The general structure of the dye anions can be represented as given in Fig. 3. The compounds, $F1Cl_4Br_4$ (phloxin) and $F1Cl_4I_4$ (rose bengal), differ from $F1Br_4$ and $F1I_4$ respectively in substitution in the phthalein ring only. The chloro-substitution must produce considerable steric hindrance to coplanarity with the resorcin part. Even in fluorescein with no substitution, the phthalein ring is tilted by 40° – 50° . To isolate the effect of substitution of heavier halogens at various positions, the absorption spectra of these dyes are compared in pairs. For the sake of convenience, the four peaks are numbered 1, 2, 3 and 4 starting from the longest wave band.

Fig. 3. General structural formulae of fluorescein dyes

(F1 : $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = R_4 = R' = H$; $F1Cl_2$: $R_1 = R_2 = Cl$, $R_3 = R_4 = R' = H$;
 $F1I_2$: $R_1 = R_2 = I$, $R_3 = R_4 = R' = H$; $F1Br_4$: $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = R_4 = Br$, $R' = H$;
 $F1I_4$: $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = R_4 = I$, $R' = H$; $F1Cl_4Br_4$: $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = R_4 = I$, $R' = Cl$;
 $F1Cl_4I_4$: $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = R_4 = I$, $R' = Cl$).

The peak number 1 has been assigned to the x -polarized oscillation of the main chromophoric group. Feofilov's work²¹ on the polarization spectra of these dyes, indicates that the peak 4 is also due to x -polarized oscillation, whereas peaks 2 and 3 are at an angle to x -direction. They are negatively polarized compared to peaks 1 and 4. The main conclusions that can be drawn from such a comparison are : (in each case the second dye is compared with reference to the first)

- (1) No. 1 peak is red shifted by any substitution. The chloro-substitution in the phthalein ring also produces red-shift.
- (2) *Di-chloro and di-iodo*—No. 1 peak is red shifted but a blue shift is observed for No. 2 peak. It may be due to oscillation in y -direction. It is likely that the large I atoms will distort the ring to certain extent causing blue shift of peak 2.
- (3) *Di-iodo and tetra-iodo*—red shift for all peaks, general effect of more polarizable substituents.
- (4) *Tetra-bromo and tetra-iodo*—red shift for all peaks, spectra almost superimposable when shifted by 8 nm—general effect of more polarizable substituents.
- (5) *Eosin and phloxin* ; erythrosin and rose bengal—main band red-shifted, peaks 2 and 3 not much affected, but peak 4 distorted. This distortion, shown in Fig. 2 can be explained if a hidden peak is present in that region.
- (6) *Phloxin and rose bengal*—Peak 1 red shifted, other peaks almost coincident. The substitution in the phthalein ring distorts the peak 4. It has been assigned to x -oscillation in the benzene ring. The highly substituted phthalein ring may also have an absorption in this region.

Effect of Halo-Substitution : In a discussion on the effect of halo-substitution on conjugated systems both the electron donating property of halogens through mesomeric effect of p -orbital conjugation and the electron withdrawing property of halogens through d -orbital resonance have to be considered. Halogens are electron withdrawing through inductive effects also. In the excited state the polarizability of the halogens becomes important. The two above mentioned processes compete and therefore physical and chemical properties of such systems may not always follow a systematic order of F, Cl, Br and I, but may present a jumbled up sequence as regards the variation of properties on halo-substitution. It also depends whether the ground state property or the excited state property is involved.

The general shift of the main absorption band of these dyes on substitution, even when non-coplanar phthalein ring is substituted, follows the general order of the atomic polarizabilities of halogens. A plot of $\bar{\nu}_{max}$ versus $\Sigma\alpha_t$ where $\Sigma\alpha_t$ is the sum of the atomic polarizabilities of the substituted halogens is linear (Fig. 4) with little scatter of points. The values of atomic polarizabilities of F, Cl, Br and I are 0.38, 2.28, 3.34 and 5.11 respectively. It therefore may appear that the main contribution to the red-shift is due to the variation in the polarizability of the substituents.

Effect of Solvent : The effect of solvent on the absorption maxima is also interesting. As compared to aqueous solution, the spectra of fluorescein and all the halogen derivatives are shifted to longer wavelengths in ethanol and glycerol (Table 2), which is rather contrary

to what is expected in a solvent of low dielectric constant. Because of this shift it has been suggested that the excited state for fluorescein is less polar than the ground state.²²

Fig. 4. Plot of $\bar{\nu}_{max}$ against $\Sigma\alpha_i$

TABLE 2

$\bar{\nu}_{max}$ in different solvents for fluorescein and halofluorescein dyes

Dye	$\bar{\nu}_{max} \times 10^{-3} \text{ (cm}^{-1}\text{)}$			$\delta\bar{\nu}_{EtOH} \text{ (cm}^{-1}\text{)}$	$\delta\bar{\nu}_{Glyc} \text{ (cm}^{-1}\text{)}$
	water	ethanol	glycerol	$(\bar{\nu}_{maxH_2O} - \bar{\nu}_{maxEtOH})$	$(\bar{\nu}_{maxH_2O} - \bar{\nu}_{maxGlyc})$
Fl	20.37	19.92	19.96	450	410
Fl ₂	19.61	19.27	19.31	340	300
FlBr ₄	19.31	18.94	18.98	370	330
FlCl ₄ I ₄	18.48	18.12	18.18	360	300

The last two columns of table 2 give the solvent shift with reference to aqueous solution, $\delta\bar{\nu}_{EtOH}$ and $\delta\bar{\nu}_{Glyc}$ for a number of halo-fluoresceins. It is observed that the difference in transition energy is greater for the unsubstituted fluorescein as compared to the halo-substituted fluoresceins. In the ground state, the end heteroatoms carry an excess of negative charge and are therefore exposed to strong hydration. On excitation, charge migration towards the ring occurs and solvation of the heteroatoms is reduced. This may cause a decreased stabilization of the excited state as compared to the ground state thereby increasing the difference between the two levels. Since the solvation by ethanol and glycerol is expected to be less than that due to water, the relative stabilization of the ground state will be smaller in these cases, causing red shift.

On halo substitution, as in FII_2 , the electron withdrawing properties of the halogens due to $d\pi$ -participation becomes important and charge migration may occur from the oxygen to the halogens through the conjugated ring system. Therefore both the energy states involved in the transition will be less solvated than those of the unsubstituted fluorescein. Although a slightly higher transition energy, as compared to alcohol and glycerol will be observed for the aqueous solutions, the effect will be less. Any further halo-substitution does not affect the $\delta\bar{\nu}_{\text{EtOH}}$ values any more. The substitution effect for both the states must be similar. It appears that for the unsubstituted dye the solute-solvent dipole-dipole interactions contribute substantially to the total solvent effect.

It has already been mentioned that $\bar{\nu}_{\text{max}}$ for the series of halo-fluoresceins in aqueous solutions can be correlated with $\Sigma\alpha_i$, the sum of atomic polarizabilities of the halo-substituents. (Fig. 4). Except for unsubstituted fluorescein a plot of $\log K$ versus $\Sigma\alpha_i$ is also linear for halo-fluorescein in aqueous solution as reported earlier²⁷. It does appear that the main contribution towards dye aggregation is from the dispersion force interaction for more polarizable molecules. Such a trend may also arise if charge transfer interactions are involved.

Aggregation properties of dyes are not confined to aqueous solutions only. The dimerization constant K at 28° for the series of halo-substituted fluoresceins in the three solvents under study are given in Table 3. Although water is the best medium for aggregation, fairly large K values are obtained in ethanol and glycerol, the order being $K_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} > K_{\text{Glyc}} > K_{\text{EtOH}}$. Furthermore, a plot of $\log K$ against $\bar{\nu}_{\text{max}}$ (Fig. 5) is linear for all the three

Fig. 5. Plot of $\log K$ against $\bar{\nu}_{\text{max}}$.

- — Water
- — Glycerol
- △ — Ethanol

solvents, the point for fluorescein being off the line. All the three straight lines are more or less parallel to each other indicating that similar forces are involved in all the three solvents and the cause for variation in \bar{v}_{max} is probably also the driving force for aggregation.

TABLE 3

Variation in dimerization constant K for halofluoresceins in ethanol and glycerol with reference to that in water expressed in terms of $\delta \log K_{EtOH}$ and $\delta \log K_{Gly}$.

Dye	$\delta \log K_{EtOH}$ ($\log K_{H_2O} - \log K_{EtOH}$)	$\delta \log K_{Gly}$ ($\log K_{H_2O} - \log K_{Gly}$)
Fl	0.14	0.10
FlI ₂	0.14	0.08
FlBr ₄	0.15	0.09
FlCl ₄ I ₄	0.18	0.14

The difference between the $\log K$ values in EtOH and glycerol with reference to water is given in the last two columns of Table 3. The difference is slightly higher for rose bengal in both the series. If it is assumed that for similar differences similar mechanism is operative, then for rose bengal which has a fairly high aggregation property, the $\log K$ value for water should be obtainable by adding (a) 0.14 to $\log K_{EtOH}$ and (b) 0.10 to $\log K_{Gly}$:

$$(a) 2.22 + 0.14 = 2.36 \quad \text{and} \quad (b) 2.26 + 0.09 = 2.35$$

which will predict a value of $K_{H_2O} = 224$ (the antilog of 2.36). But the experimental value is slightly higher (table 1, column 4) than the value predicted on the basis of single mechanism for aggregation in all the three solvents. A single case of slightly higher value may not be too significant here but it does point to additional factors coming into play for highly aggregating dyes. It will be interesting to study the solvent effect on other series of highly aggregating dyes to bring out this point. A study of the thermodynamic parameters may throw some light on this aspect.

The thermodynamic parameters for the aggregation of these dyes are very revealing.²³ From the temperature effect on the dimerization constants, the standard values for free energy change ΔG° , enthalpy ΔH° and entropy ΔS° at 28° are tabulated in table 4. Because 28°C of the very low aggregation tendency of the unsubstituted fluorescein, it has not been possible to obtain these values for this dye from the absorption data alone.²⁴

TABLE 4

log K at two different temperatures and the values of ΔG° , ΔH° and ΔS° derived therefrom at 28°C

Dye	log K		ΔG° (k cal)	ΔH° (k cal)	ΔS° (cal/°K)
	28°	12°			
FlI ₂	1.919	2.223	-2.65	-7.90	-17
FlBr ₄	2.041	2.318	-2.82	-7.05	-14
FlI ₄	2.146	2.320	-2.97	-6.50	-12
FlCl ₄ I ₄	2.398	2.586	-3.31	-4.90	-5

From the nature of variation of ΔG° and ΔH° one can at once see that the nature of forces responsible for aggregation are changing on continued halo-substitution. Whereas free energy change increases, enthalpy change is reduced. The trend in the values of ΔH° and ΔS° suggests that the process is gradually changing over from enthalpy directed one to entropy directed one. It is normally expected that the process of dimerization should proceed with decrease in entropy. But gradual gain in entropy for more polarizable molecules suggests some other source of entropy increase. The only other source available is the solvent. The breaking of water structure may contribute substantially towards less negative entropy change suggesting increased hydrophobic interaction in more aggregating dyes. These interactions are not due to specific solvation. The specific solvation is largest for fluorescein and in that system hydrogen bonding through solvent may be a mechanism for dimerisation. But in less solvated systems, dispersion force interaction is the predominant aggregating force. As the system changes further on substitution of heavier halogens, hydrophobic contribution tends to increase. The origin of hydrophobicity is not clear as yet but it has been ascribed to van der Waals forces on the surface of the molecule which is reflected in surface tension as also in the insolubility of non-polar molecules in aqueous medium. In the system under study, aggregation occurs between two dye anions, each with two units of negative charge. The estimated entropy factor for such a dimer, at a separation distance of 4 Å should be about -20 e.u. for purely electrostatic interactions in aqueous medium. Less loss of entropy than the theoretical value will have substantial contribution from this structural entropy ΔS_{st}^{25} . Since for most of the dyes studied ΔS is about -6 e.u., $\Delta S_{st} \approx 14$ e.u.

The coming together of two similarly charged particles will normally be hindered due to electrostatic interaction. No doubt there is some contribution from this effect since $\log K$ decreases with D , the solvent permittivity. But the variation of ionic strength by addition of KNO_3 tends to lower the dimerization constant slightly. This is contrary to the expected behaviour for interaction between like charges but in systems of delocalised charges, the electrostatic contribution may be small. It rather seems that the counter ions tend to localise the charge and thereby reduce the charge oscillation. This in turn may lead to reduced aggregation tendency due to decreased dispersive interaction. Furthermore although the addition of urea should increase the dielectric constant of the solution and enhance association, it is generally observed to act as a deaggregating agent²⁶ is evidently due to its structure breaking action on water. Looking at the thermodynamic parameters, it is evident that there is not complete compensation of ΔH and ΔS in the series of substituted fluoresceins. There is some residual enthalpy although the relationship between $-\Delta H$ and $-T\Delta S$ is linear²³.

From spectrophotometric studies the interaction energies between dye dimers of this series are found to increase in the series and the dimer geometry to be such that the two component molecules are twisted by an angle θ along the dimer axis²⁷. Mukherjee and Ghosh²⁸ have reported that for methylene blue, trimerisation constant is greater than dimerization constant. From these considerations it can be suggested that the dye polymers are stacked one over the other, each twisted by an angle θ with respect to the nearest neighbour and in a helical fashion²⁷ held together mainly by dispersion forces, hydrophobic interactions becoming important for highly aggregating dyes.

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